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Buddhist Councils and their Effect on Buddhist Literature

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Abstract: This paper is presented with a view to enabling to know that the dhammas preached by the Buddha are existing well organized as Buddhist Literature in the forms of Sutta, Vinaya and Dhamma due to the benefits of the six conventions of Saṅgāyanā that are accepted by the Theravada Buddhists. After the Parinibbāna of the Buddha, the dhammas preached by the Buddha for 45 years were systematically collected after questioning, answering and collective recitation. Moreover the dhammas that were scattered could be analytically collected and recorded as a literature in Dhamma and Vinaya. Those who are in the pursuit of Piṭaka literature are able to show exactly and materially what kind of person the Buddha was and what kind of practice the Buddha's instruction was. Moreover the new generation Buddhists can firmly believe that these dhammas were the instructions delivered by the Buddha himself. By holding Saṅgāyanā conventions, the Buddha's dhammas can be preserved by handing over from one generation to another through the successive ages. The handing over of the Buddhist literature is the main factor of perpetuation of Buddha Sāsana. This is the greatest benefit of Saṅgāyanā conventions.

Keywords: effect, Buddhist council, convention

Introduction

Out of the world's countries, Myanmar is the country where the majority of the populations are Buddhists. The majority of the citizens abide by the Buddha's teaching. They were the dhammas such as *dānakathā* (talk on charity), *sīlakathā* (talk on morality), etc. preached by the Buddha for 45 vassa years over 2500 years ago. At that time, there was no literature in the history of literature. There was no Scripture and there was no written literature or composition. But beginning from the time of Buddha's *Parinibbāna*, the remaining elder

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Theras such as Venerable Mahākassapa could preserve the Buddha *dhammas* by holding the conventions of *Saṅgāyanā*. The *dhammas* preserved by holding *Saṅgāyanā* conventions are recognized as *Tipiṭaka*, five *Nikāyas*, etc. and also as *Sutta*, *Vinaya* and *Abhidhamma*. Moreover the disciplinary rules of conduct prescribed by the Buddha can also be preserved as the original.

The Term “*Saṅgāyanā*”

Saṅgāyanā is a combination of words: *saṃ* + *√gā* + *y* + *ana* + *ā*. It connotes “united recitation¹”, Moreover it is expounded in *Sārattha Dīpanī Tīkā* as: “*Yathā paccayaṃ tattha tattha desi tathā paññitā ca vipa kiṇṇānaṃ dhamma vinayānaṃ saṅgahtvā gāyana kathanam*”. The meaning is “the similar *dhammavinayas* that were preached here and there scatteringly are recited in unison.²”

The term “*saṅgīti*” that is found firmly in the *Tipiṭaka* is irrefutably found in *Saṅgīti Sutta* which is the tenth *sutta* in *Pāthika Vagga* in *Dīgha Nikāya*. Venerable *Sāriputta* preached this *Sutta* in the mango garden of *Cunda* Goldsmith of *Pāvā* town, *Mallā* Province about ten years before the Buddha’s *Parinibbāna*. In that *sutta* Venerable *Sāriputta* preached that as the *dhamma* was well expounded by the Buddha in this *Sutta*, it was replete with *svakhāto* attribute, that it was *Niyānika Sāsanā* that enables the beings to be liberated from the round of repeated births, that it was *Upasama Sāsanā* that extinguishes the defilements, and it was *dhammavinaya* that was preached with perfect self-enlightenment knowledge. Therefore *Dhammavinaya* that were *svakhata* and *Niyānika* must be guarded by all unanimously. According to Venerable *Mahā Buddhaghosa*, “*Saṅgāyitabbam*” preached by Venerable *Sāriputta* must be uniformly recited without any deviation³.

The Effects of the First *Saṅgāyanā* Convention

The account of the first *Saṅgāyanā* Convention was found the earliest in *Pañcapatikakkhandhaka*, *Cūla Vagga Pāḷi*, *Vinaya Piṭaka*⁴. The First *Saṅgāyanā* Convention was celebrated in *Sattapaṇṇi* Cave on the *Vebhāra* Hillside near *Rājagaha* three months after the *parinibbāna* of the Buddha. Venerable *Mahākassapa* led the *Saṅgāyanā* Convention by serving as *Samgha Nāyaka*. Five hundred *Arahant Theras* such as Venerable *Upāli*, Venerable *Ānandā*, etc. committed the Three *Piṭakas* to memory for seven months⁵.

¹ Pā myan dhān, 946.

² Sāṭi I. 26.

³ Thin-gar -mine, 1-6.

⁴ Vi IV, 31.

⁵ Pāsarmine, 260-1.

The primary cause of the convention of *Saṅgāyanā* was among the follower monks of Venerable *Mahā Kassapa*, those who were not free from defilements wept vehemently when they learnt of the death of the Buddha. Those who were free from defilements reflected on the impermanency of the physical and mental phenomena⁶. At that time, a monk called *Subhaddā* who became a monk in his old age said to the lamenting monks, “Friends, do not grieve and do not weep. Now we are free from the hands of the great *Samaṇa Gotama* who has oppressed us by saying, “This is proper for you; that is not proper for you! From now on, we can do what we like.”⁷

On hearing these disrespectful words, Venerable *Mahā Kassapa* was struck with awe. After the cremation of Buddha’s corpse and distribution of the sacred relics, *Venerable Mahā Kassapa* told the words of the monk and among the assembly of the *Samṅha* and made decision to hold the *Saṅgāyanā* convention together with *Samṅha*⁸.

By holding the convention of *Saṅgāyanā*, the danger of *adhammavādīs* like *Subhadda* monk could be warded off. Moreover, the most obvious point is the fact the *dhammas* preached by the Buddha can be preserved without any omission, addition and deletion up to the present time⁹. *Vinaya* was collected under the leadership of Venerable *Upāli* Thera and *Dhamma* was organized under the leadership of Venerable *Ānandā* Thera. As each *dhamma* was questioned and answered in detail and recited unanimously, *Dhamma* and *Vinaya* could be distinguished and recorded. It is conducive to the four prime causes of the organization of *Vinaya*, the organization of *Dhamma*, investigation of Venerable *Ānandā* and inflicting Brahma penalty on *Chanda* monk.

The successive emergence of *Saṅgāyanā* in the long history of Buddhist literature is not only consequence of the First *Saṅgāyanā* Convention but also the benefits of long-lasting existence of the *Sāsanā*.

The Effects of the Second *Saṅgāyanā* Convention

In 100 B.E. the Second *Saṅgāyanā* Convention was held by seven hundred Arahats under the leadership of such as Venerable *Revata*, Venerable *Sabbakāmi*, etc. under the leadership of Venerable *Yasa Thera* and the sponsorship of King *Kālāsoka* of *Vesālī* Kingdom at *Vālukārāma* Monastery¹⁰.

⁶ D II,134.

⁷ Buddhatharthanartaw, 1-4.

⁸ D A I, 3-4.

⁹ Vi IV, 384.

¹⁰ Pāsarmaing, 261.

The effects of this *Saṅgāyanā* Conventions are the amendments of the *Vinaya* disciplinary rules violated by monks residing in *Vajji* province. They are:-

- (1) *Siṅgīloṅakappa* – salt placed in animal horn is consumed as eatables,
- (2) *Dvaṅgukappa* – partaking of alms food till two fingers' breadth of shadow beyond noon,
- (3) *Gāmantakappa* – eating alms food at another village by a monk who incurs *pavārita apatti*,
- (4) *Āvāsakappa* – observance of separate religious duties within a new ordination hall,
- (5) *Anumatikappa* – doing penance after securing approval of the absent monks,
- (6) *Āciṅṅakappa* – practising all the practices of the preceptor teacher,
- (7) *Amathitakappa* – the monk who incurs *pavārita* offence drinking milk before reaching the state of curd,
- (8) *Jaḷogi* – drinking light alcoholic drink,
- (9) *Adasakanisīdana* – using fringeless cushion,
- (10) *Jātarūparajata* – receiving offerings of gold, silver.

These ten points could be confirmed unanimously that they are *adhammavattus* which are not in accord with the *Vinaya* rules¹¹. Moreover Buddha's *Vinaya* could be purified by suppressing *adhammavādīs*¹².

The Effects of the Third *Saṅgāyanā* Convention

In 235 B.E. the Third *Saṅgāyanā* Convention was held by 1000 Arahats under the leadership of Venerable Mahāmoggaliputta Tissa *Thera* at Asokarāma Monastery in Pāṭaliputta city for nine months. The patron of the *Saṅgāyanā* convention was King Sīridhammāsoka¹³. By holding *Saṅgāyanā* convention, encroaching of wrongful views into the Doctrine of the Buddha could be prevented. Venerable Mahāmoggaliputta Tissa *Thera* and King Sīridhammāsoka could also dispatch nine missions to the nine regions. As Mahāmoggaliputta Tissa expounded in detail the *dhammas* preached by the Buddha briefly, there emerged *Kathāvatthu* treatise. Furthermore, it could also be carried out for a continuous development of Buddhism in Ceylon.

The Effects of the Fourth *Saṅgāyanā* Convention

The people of Sri Lanka were hit hard by rebels, hunger and starvation for 12 years. So the monks had to make strong efforts to maintain the Buddha's teaching. The elder *theras* foresaw that if there would appear such danger in future the monks would not be able to memorize the discourses and the *vinaya* rules by heart because of the decline of their power

¹¹ Vi IV, 469.

¹² *Buddhasāsanāta*, 57-60.

¹³ *Pāsarmine*, 261.

of mindfulness, concentration and wisdom. Therefore the Fourth *saṅgāyanā* Convention was held by five hundred *arahant theras* under the leadership of Venerable Mahādhamma Rakkhita in *Aloka* Cave near *Malaya* village in Sri Lanka in 450 B.E. (first century B.C). At this *Saṅgāyanā* convention, the Buddha's *dhammas* were committed to inscription on palm-leaves. The convention of the *saṅgāyanā* was supported by King Abhaya Vatteḡāmaṇi¹⁴. The Fourth *saṅgāyanā* Convention was the most significant for the Buddhists for all the teachings of the Buddha, namely, *sutta*, *vinaya* and *abhidhamma* could be committed to inscription on palm-leaves for the first time in the Buddhist history. As the palm-leaf manuscripts were examined for a hundred times it was a *saṅgāyanā* that is the cause of non-extinction and long-lasting of the Buddha's *dhammas*, At that time the monks suffered much from the rebels, hunger and starvation. If these monks could not preserve these *dhammas*, the *dhammas* could not exist until today. Therefore the Buddhists can abide by the *dhammas* of the Buddha thanks to the Fourth *saṅgāyanā* Convention.

The Effects of the Fifth *Saṅgāyanā* Convention

The fifth *saṅgāyanā* Convention was held in the golden pavilion of the place for six months in 2415 B.E., 1233 M.E., 1871 A.D. The Buddha's *piṭakas* were committed to inscription on 729 marble slabs. The *piṭakas* were recited by 2400 learned monks unanimously. The leading noble *theras* were Venerable Jāgarābhivaṃsa, Venerable Narindābhidhaja and Venerable Sumaṅgala Sāmi. The patron of the four material requisites was King Mindon¹⁵.

King Mindon ascended the throne in 2396 B.E. eight years after ascending the throne, King Mindon caused the learned *sayadaws* to edit the *piṭakas*. Then the *piṭakas* were committed to inscription on palm-leaves. Starting from the full-moon day of *tazaungmon* in 2404 B.E. and 1222 M.E. the *piṭakas* were committed to gold inscription, ink inscription, and stylus inscription and then the *piṭakas* were kept in the *piṭaka taik* at the foot of Mandalay Hill.

Moreover King Mindon had the palm-leaf manuscripts made by successive kings committed to inscription on stone for long-lasting of the *sāsana*. On committing the *piṭakas* to inscription on stone, the monk scholars and lay scholars had to supervise the inscription on stone so that there were no deviations in alphabet, word, text and punctuation mark. There are 729 stone slabs. Each stone slab enshrined in a separate brick building with a tiered roof within the enclosures of *Kuthodaw* Pagoda at the foot of Mandalay Hill. Now *Kuthodaw* Pagoda is being recognized as the World's Biggest Book¹⁶.

¹⁴ Pāsarmine, 262.

¹⁵ Pāsarmine, 262-3.

¹⁶ Buddhanaingantaw III.161-9.

Mr. H. Ripley, the owner of *hantharwady* publishing House could create the version of stone inscription in the form of printed books. The version of stone inscription was a reliable version till the Sixth *saṅgāyanā* Convention. It is still accepted as an authentic version by the world's *Therāvada* Buddhists.

The Effects of the Six *Saṅgāyanā* Convention

In committing the *piṭakas* to inscription on stone there can be errors gradually in copying from one copy to another in word, text, alphabet, sentence, chapters, etc. In order to correct these errors, the Sixth *saṅgāyanā* Convention was held at *Mahāpāsana* Cave, *Kaba-Aye* Hill, Yangon on May seventeenth 1954. The person who sponsored and served as the *saṅgha nāyaka* was Dr. Ba Oo the President of the Union of Myanmar. There were 2617 *saṅghā* who recited the *Piṭakas* unanimously under the leadership of *saṅgha nāyakas*, *saṅgharājas mahātheras* from five *theravāda* countries. At this *saṅgātanā* convention the convention was held by dividing the *Pāli* Canon, *Aṭṭhakath*, and *Ṭīkā* into five *sannipātas* (sessions). The duration of time lasted from May 21, 1934 to May 24, 1956. The benefits of the sixth *saṅgātanā* Convention were correction of errors, improving and preservation of the present-day *sāsana* and printing of the *Piṭakas* and spreading of Buddha *sāsana* all over the world¹⁷.

Conclusion

Buddha sāsana is the *sāsana* that lays down rules of conduct for the monks and *sāmaṇeras* and rules of conduct for the human society. But the *dhamma* and *vinaya* were scattered could not be distinguished till the time of Buddha's *Parinibbāna*. Moreover when the Buddha finally passed away, there emerged persons who wanted to reform according to their option. That was why the *Mahātheras* led by Venerable *Mahakassapa* held the First *saṅgāyanā* Convention. The second *saṅgāyanā* Convention was held on account of the monks who practised in contradictory to the *vinaya* rules. Moreover the Third *saṅgāyanā* Convention was held on account of the false monks who entered monkhood for material gains. On over-viewing the benefits of these three *Saṅgāyanā* Conventions, the *dhamma* and *vinaya* preached by the Buddha before the *adhammavādīs* held the upper hand could be protected without deviation and the scattered *dhmmas* could also be distinguished distinctly. In addition at the completion of the Third *saṅgāyanā* Convention, missionary parties could be dispatched to the nine countries outside of India. At the conventions of the three *saṅgāyanā* , all the *dhamma* and *vinaya* were preserved by committing them to memory. At the Fourth *saṅgāyanā* Convention the *dhammavinaya* could not only be committed to memory but also could be committed to the inscription on palm-leaf. Moreover, during the reign of King

¹⁷ Pasarmine, 262-271.

Mindon, the Three *piṭakas* could be committed to inscription on stone at the fifth *saṅgāyanā* convention. Consequently at the Sixth *saṅgāyanā* convention, the Three *piṭakas* could be collated with stone inscription and printed so that there are no deviations in word, text, alphabet, and punctuations. Due to the beneficence of the six *saṅgāyanā*, conventions, the *dhammas* preached by the Buddha, the *Theravāda Buddhists* can only practice the Buddha's *dhammas* as the authentic exposition but also the Buddhist scholars can study the *Sutta*, *Vinaya* and *Abhidhamma* or the five *Nikāyas* by separating into sections.

Abbreviations

Pā myan dhān	<i>Pāli</i> Myanmar Abhidhan
Sāṭi I	<i>Sāratthadīpanīṭikā</i> , (<i>Pathamobhāgo</i>)
D II	Mahāvagga Pāli, (Dīgha Nikāya)
D A	Sīlakkhandhavagga Aṭṭhakathā (Dīgha Nikāya)
Vi IV	Cūḷa vagga Pāli (Vinaya Piṭaka)
Pāsarmine	<i>Pāli</i> Sarpaythamine
Buddhanaingantaw	Buddhanaingantaw
Buddhatharthanartaw	Buddhatharthanartaw, 2500 Khayee

References

- Ant, Mg (1995) *Buddhatharthanartaw, 2500 Khayee*, Ministry of Religious Affairs, Yangon.
- Buddhaghosa, Mahāthera (2002) *Sīlakkhandhavagga Aṭṭhakathā*, Department of Religious Affairs Press, Yangon.
- Hote Sein, U (1954) *Pāli* Myanmar Abhidhan, Union of Myanmar Government, Yangon.
- Ohn, Daw (1981) *Pāli* Sarpaythamine, Ministry of Religious Affairs, Yangon.
- Saṃsarābhivaṃsa, Ashin (2007) *Buddhanaingantaw*, Ministry of Religious Affairs, Yangon.
- (1957) *Māhāvagga Pāli*, Ministry of Religious Affairs, Yangon.
- (1960) *Sāratthadīpanīṭikā*, (*Pathamobhāgo*), Myanmar Buddhists Missionary Press, Yangon.
- (1989) *Cūḷvagga Pāli*, Ministry of Religious Affairs, Yangon.

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